

Collaborative Study and an Expression of Visual Narrative in Three Dimensional (3-D) Art Form in Front of the Main Gate at the Federal College Of Education (Technical) Asaba Towards Tackling the Challenges of Poor Enrolment into the College

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Abstract

This is a collaborative study and visual narrative in three dimensional (3-d) art forms which was mounted at the main gate of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. It was executed with a view to tackling the challenges of poor enrolment into the college. The study focused on obtaining inputs from various sampled departments in randomly selected Schools, about the design elements and symbols, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the sampled Schools in the College, in order to develop preliminary sketches, working drawings. Moreover the study utilized the selected design elements and symbols, to produce a three dimensional (3-D) in front of the college gate. The researchers adopted the art-based action research and a survey to obtain information from various Departments, about the appropriateness of the design elements and symbols, that best portrayed the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the sampled departments in the College. Furthermore, various materials, tools and the step-by-step processes were described in details. Findings revealed that the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing reflected the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various departments of the college and that the selected design elements and symbols, was utilized to produce a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate. It then recommended that More Tetfund research grants should be made available to sponsor similar researches in the feature, and that an assessment to ascertain the extent to which the project was able to achieve its objective should be conducted after a period of five years.

Keywords: Philosophy and objectives, Collaborative study, Visual narrative, Design elements and Symbols, Three dimensional (3-d) arts, Sculpture-on-the-round

Background to the Study

The erection of outdoor sculptures in an academic institution and indeed a College of Education, should not only serve to provide aesthetic value but also be utilized as an effective visual vocabulary to chronicle the story of the institution for the students, other members of the college community as well as members of the larger community, playing host to the institution. Such works should be able to convey the right message and equally provide aesthetic value and enjoyment in the environment. Obviously sculptural works are perhaps some of the most utilized art works for such purposes. These types of art works are viewed as public art and are executed in Urban Public Spaces.

Davari (2014) is of the view that the quality and use of public space is a fundamental issue that affects people's interactions. He also asserted that urban planners and urban designers around the world look to public art as an opportunity to create lively and dynamic public spaces. To this end, public art has become a vital tool not only to increase the quality and aesthetics of urban spaces but also to help satisfy the social and cultural needs of the people. The author under reference further stressed that public art can be used to express the identity and characteristic of public spaces and that in this regard art has a primary role in creation of positive or negative public spaces. Moreover, Remesar (2005) is of the view that the art executed in public spaces indicates the present social and cultural situation, as well as the artistic and aesthetic tendencies.

Cement and stone survives far better than works of art in other materials, and often represents the majority of the surviving works of public sculpture from ancient cultures, while acrylic paint which are water based paints are perhaps the most widely used for mural paintings (Wikipedia, 2018). Obviously, the erection of sculptural works in the landscape settings in an academic institution not only provides the sculptural work with new meaning but also provides a new meaning and understanding of the site. Such works can demonstrate how art, when placed in either significant or intimately scaled landscape settings, can contribute to the shared memory and iconography of the campus.

Statement of the problem

Despite the numerous advantages and environmental benefits of public art such as an outdoor sculpture to an institutional environment, the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, do not seem to have any of such public art at the entrance of the College. Moreover it seems as if many people are not conversant with the type of programmes that are offered in the College. Yet the erection of such public art work would not only help to enhance the aesthetic quality of the environment but can also serve as an effective tool and visual vocabulary to help narrate the story of the institution as well as convey the right message about various programmes mounted in the college to the larger members of the community. It is against this background that a collaborative study and visual narrative in three (3) dimensional art forms at the front of the main gate at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, was executed. The researchers envision the utilization of an action research in the production of a sculpture-on-the-round (3-D) in front of the main gate which is the main entrance into the College. Thus, a design concept that carefully considered the goals of the College was visually represented.

The Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this research was to collaborate with sampled schools and departments in the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, to conduct a visual study that resulted in the production of a three dimensional (3-D) art form, which was erected in front of the main gate of the college, with a view to tackling challenges of

inadequate information about the college programmes through the use of public art. Specifically, the study sought to:

- Determine from the inputs of sampled schools and departments, the design elements and symbols, that best portrayed the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the sampled departments in the selected schools in the College.
- Develop preliminary sketches, working drawings using inputs from sampled schools and departments, about the design elements and symbols, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the departments of the selected schools in the College.
- Utilize the selected design elements and symbols, from sampled schools and departments, to produce a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate.

Research Questions

The following research questions have been raised to address the study objectives:

- What are the design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in various Departments of the College?
- To what extent do the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing reflect the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various Departments of the college? To what extent are the selected design elements and symbols, utilized to produce a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate?

Significance of the Study

The following are the Significance of the Study:

- This study is vital as it would not only help make the front of the main entrance into the College aesthetically appealing, but also help advertise the programmes in the College. Indeed the art work would not only serve to enhance the aesthetic quality of the environment at the main gate of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, but also serve to inform all stakeholders about the various programmes mounted, in various Departments of the College.
- The art work would also serve to preserve the College vision and mission, which will be visually illustrated by the finished art work.
- The information that would be visually narrated can help stir-up students' interest in the programmes mounted in the college thereby improving student's enrollment into the College.
- The Art work can equally help stimulate interest in Fine and Applied Arts thereby improve the students' enrollment in the art programme in the College.

- The research would create an opportunity for collaboration across various disciplines in the College as inputs from various Departments would be required to create the final design for the art work.

Scope of the Study

This is a collaborative study that utilized inputs from sampled disciplines in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba to visually present programmes offered in the College. The selected design elements and symbols were utilized to execute a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate.

Methodology

The Design of the Study

The study is an art-based action research. Wilson and Flicker, (2014) defined an Arts-based action research as the use of the arts, in various forms, as the basis for inquiry, intervention, knowledge production and information sharing. The approaches consist of the merging of the conventions of 'traditional' qualitative methodologies with those of the arts to allow for deeper research insight, interpretation, meaning making and creative expression, as well as alternative knowledge and ways of knowing.

In this study, the researchers utilized the art-based action research methodology to obtain data from various Departments, on the design elements and symbols, that best portray the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in various Departments of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. They also organized some Arts students, along with themselves to produce a three dimensional (3-D) high-relief on the two side wall of the College gate and a bas-relief sculpture on the horizontal slab or platform on top of the gate house, as a means to sensitize students, and the community on the philosophy and objectives of the programmes in the college. Furthermore, various materials, tools and the step-by-step processes that were used in executing the art work were described in details so as to reveal how the work evolved.

Population for the Study

All the twenty-seven (24) Departments in seven (8) schools of the College made up the total population for the study. Table 1 below gives a summary of the number of schools and departments in Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

Table 1 : Summary of Number of schools and Departments

S/N	Names of Schools	Number of Departments
1	Adult, Non-formal and Special Education	1
2	Education	4
3	Early childhood care and primary Education	2
4	School of General Education	1
5	School of Secondary Education (Business)	2
6	School of Secondary Education (Sciences)	6
7	School of Secondary Education (Technical)	5
8	School of Secondary Education (Vocational)	3
Total		24

Sample and Sampling Technique

The purposive random sampling techniques would be adopted for the study. The sampling technique was used to select four (4) from the eight (8) schools that form the population for the study. These four (4) schools made up fifty percent (50%) of the total population that was used for the study.

Moreover one (1) department each was randomly selected for the study. They are tabulated as follows:

S/N	Name of School	Department
1	Education	Education
2	School of Secondary Education (Sciences)	Biology
3	School of Secondary Education (Technical)	Automobile
4	School of Secondary Education (Vocational)	Fine and Applied art

The design elements and symbols from these for schools and departments were used to develop preliminary drawings and the final working drawing that was used to portray the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, the sampled departments in the College.

The following elements and symbols were used to produce the final drawing:

Plate 1: A Composition of a Graduation Cap, Books and Certificate.(Design Element and Symbol for School of Education)

Plate 2: A Microscope. Design Element and Symbol for School of Secondary Education (Science)

Plate 3: A Composition of a Hand Holding a Spanner. Design Element and Symbol for School of Secondary Education (Technical)

Plate 4: A Composition of a Paint Pallet, a Brush and a Pencil. Design Element and Symbol for School of Secondary Education (Vocational)

Plate 5: A sewing machining which is also the design element and symbol for School of Secondary Education (Vocational)

Plate 6: Logo of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba

Plate 7 which is the sketch that bore the college logo was selected for the visual study and formed the sketch from which the working drawing (plate 8) was developing.

These design elements and symbols used for the composition were further developed into a questionnaire as research instrument to help answer the first and the second research questions (RQ1 & RQ2). The research instrument (preliminary sketches and a five point scale close-type questionnaire) was used to determine, the effectiveness of the sketch in conveying concept of advertising the academic programmes in the college as well as enhancing the aesthetic quality of the gate that leads to the entrance into the college. A total of 22 questionnaires were produce and distributed to respondents. The completed questionnaires were analyzed using descriptive statistics including mean and frequency count. Responses were converted to numerical code (SA = 4; A= 3; D = 2; SD = 1). However, Production method would be used to answer the third research question (RQ3).

Materials used for the Production of the sculptural work

The first stage was the development of preliminary sketch and working drawing while final stage involved the erection of seven feet (7ft) high sculptural work executed in cement using direct modeling technique. To this end, the following materials were required:

1	Rods 16mm	used for central armature reinforcement
2	Rods 10mm	used for construction of grid network of armature
3	Rods 8mm	used for construction of grid network of armature
4	Rods ¼	used for construction of grid network of armature
5	Bags of Cement	used for production of sculptural work and casting the pedestal
6	A trip Sand	used for production of sculptural work and casting the pedestal
7	Scaffold	used for climbing to execute work at high elevation
8	A tanker Water	used for mixing the sand and cement composite
9	Wire gauze	used for the construction work sculptural slab
10	Binding wire	used as armature support
11	Welding works	used for joining all the rods within the grid network of the armature together
12	Gold dust	used for partination (finishing) of art work
13	Car paint (different colours)	used for partination (finishing) of art work
14	Some Blocks	used for casting the pedestal on which the sculptural work was erected
15	A trip of Gravel	To reinforce the sculptural work and casting the pedestal

Data Analysis and Interpretation of Result

This section focused on the data analysis and presentation of result. The mean statistics was used for the data analysis of research question one, while research question two was answered through the production method

Research Question One

What are the design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in various Departments of the College?

Table 3: Responses to question item on visual expression relating to School of Education

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	RMK
1	Plate 1 is a composition of an academic cap, some book and a certificate	44	24	0	0	3.5	Agree
2	Teacher training is the over-all goal of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	56	24	0	0	3.6	Agree
3	The composition in plate 4 visually expresses the ultimate goal of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	48	30	0	0	3.5	Agree
4	Utilizing the image in plate 4 in producing a sculptural design will be able to visually express the over-all goal of programmes at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	36	39		00	3.4	Agree
GRAND MEAN						3.4	Agree

Table 3 shows that all of the respondents were of the view that the design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in the School of Education, Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

All of the respondents were in agreement with items , 1, 2,3 and 4 which bother on the adequacy of the design element and symbol develop to visually express the School of Education. The grand mean of 3.4 further attested to the submission that the design was adequate for reflecting the programmes in the School of Education.

Table 4: Responses to question item on visual expression relating to School of Secondary Education (Sciences)

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	RMK
5	Plate 2 is a visual expression of a microscope	60	21	0	0	3.7	Agree
6	The microscope is an important teaching material to teach science education	56	24	0	0	3.6	Agree
7	The diagram can be said to adequately represent School of secondary Education (science) in the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	88	6	0	0	4.3	Agree
8	When included in a sculptural design it can be used to visually express the programmes mounted in the School of secondary Education (science) at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	72	12	0	0	3.8	Agree
GRAND MEAN						3.6	Agree

Moreover, table 4 revealed that all of the respondents were of the view that the design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, best portrayed the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in the School of Secondary Education (Science) at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

All of the respondents were in agreement with items , 5, 6,7 and 8 which bothered on capability of the design element and symbol develop to visually express the School of Secondary Education (Science). The grand mean of 3.6 further indicated that the design was adequate for reflecting the programmes in the School of Secondary Education (Science).

Table 5: Responses to question item on visual expression relating to School of Secondary Education (Technical)

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	RMK
9	The diagram in plate 3 a, represents the teaching materials used in most of the courses in the School of secondary Education (Technical)	72	12	0	0	3.8	Agree
10	The composition in the plate is used to visual express the programme mounted in the School of secondary Education (Technical)	60	21	0	0	3.7	Agree
11	Plate 3 reveals that the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba houses a technical programme	8	66	0	0	3.4	Agree
12	When included in the composition of a sculptural design, it will adequately inform people about the technical programmes mounted in the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	68	15	0	0	3.8	Agree
GRAND MEAN						3.4	Agree

Similarly, table 5 also revealed that all of the respondents were of the view that the design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, best portrayed the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in the School of Secondary Education (Technical) at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

All of the respondents were in agreement with items 9, 10,11 and 12. Similarly, The grand mean of 3.4 also indicated that the design was adequate for reflecting the programmes in the School of Secondary Education (Technical).

Table 6: Responses to question item on visual expression relating to School of Secondary Education (Vocational)

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	RMK
13	Plate 4 and 5 are some Fine and Applied materials/equipment	44	24	0	0	3.5	Agree
14	One of the material /equipment is also used for Home Economics	56	24	0	0	3.6	Agree
15	Both textile design and clothing and textile are related	48	30	0	0	3.5	Agree
16	The composition in Plate 4 and 6 are a visual expression of the programmes mounted in the Department of Fine and Applied Arts and Home Economics Department in the School of secondary Education (vocational), Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	72	12	0	0	3.8	Agree
17	The items can be used to visually represent the Department of Fine and Applied Arts and Home Economics in the School that houses both Departments	60	21	0	0	3.7	Agree
GRAND MEAN						3.5	Agree

In the same vein, table 6 also revealed that all of the respondents were of the view that the design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, best portrayed the philosophy and

objectives of programmes mounted, in the School of Secondary Education (Technical) at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

All of the respondents were in agreement with items 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 which bothered on the capability of the design element and symbol develop to visually express the School of Secondary Education (Vocational). The grand mean of 3.5 also indicated that the design reflected the programmes in the School of Secondary Education (Vocational).

Research Question Two

To what extent do the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing reflect the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various departments of the college?

Table 7: Responses to question items on visual expression relating to the relevance of the design elements and symbols selected from sampled schools for sculptural production

	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	MEAN	RMK
18	Plate 6 is a sketch representing some programmes mounted in the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba	56	24	0	0	3.6	Agree
19	The sketch should be utilized to produce a sculptural work in front of the college gate	48	30	0	0	3.5	Agree
20	Utilizing the sketch to produce a sculptural work in front of the college gate would help advertize the programmes mounted in the college	72	12	0	0	3.8	Agree
21	The Sketch can be to used to produce a sculptural work in front of the college gate.	36	39	0	0	3.4	Agree
GRAND MEAN						3.4	Agree

Table 7 which focused on the extent to which the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing reflected the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various departments of the college, indicated that all of the respondents were in agreement that the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing reflected the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in the School of various departments of the college.

Moreover, all of the respondents were in agreement with items 18, 19, 20 and 21 which also bothered on adequacy of the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing to produce a sculptural work at the College gate. The grand mean of 3.4 also indicated that the preliminary sketches and the working drawing to produce a sculptural work at the College gate.

Research Question Three

To what extent are the selected design elements and symbols, utilized to produce a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate?

Production Procedure

The following steps were employed in the production of the sculptural edifice

Plate 6a: a view from the left before the sculptural work was erected

Plate 6b: a view from the right before the sculptural work was erected

Plate 6c: a view from the center before the sculptural work was erected

Plate 7: Digging of the foundation by a paid labourer.

Plate 8: Provision of concrete blocks and commencement of foundation to cast the pedestal on which the sculptural work was mounted

Plate 9: Erection of the foundation to cast the pedestal on which the sculptural work was mounted

Plate 10: Erecting the concrete block casing for casting the pedestal on which the sculptural work was mounted.

Plate 11: Filling the concrete block casing with gravel and sand in preparation for casting the pedestal on which the sculptural work was mounted.

Plate 12: Casting the concrete block casing revealing projected rod for producing the amateur that was use as reinforcement for the sculptural work.

Plate 13: The commencement of the sculptural production of the hand holding the spanner. This was used to depict Technical Education.

Plate 14: The microscope (depicting Science Education) and a book (which was part of the items used to depict Education) were also added to the sculptural production.

Plate 15: Another book was placed on top of the first book while an academic cap was place on top of the book. Moreover, a certificate was also place beside to the sculptural production. This composition was used to reflect the over-all goal of producing graduates in the college

Plate 16: is sculptural production of a composition of a painting pallet, a brush and a pencil. These are design element and symbol from Fine and Applied Arts Department, used to depict the School of Secondary Education (vocational) in the college.

Plate 17: The sculptural representation of a sewing machining. This is one of the design element and symbol from Fine and Applied Arts Department and that of Home Economics. It is used to depict the School of Secondary Education (vocational) in the college.

Plate 18a

Plate 18b

Plate 18c

Plate 18d

Plate 19: The Final art work title: "The programmes offered in the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. A Tedfund sponsored research erected in front of the gate of the College"

Summary of Findings

The following are the summary of the findings of the study:

- The design elements and symbols, suggested by stakeholders, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of programmes mounted, in various Departments of the College, are as follows:
 1. A Composition of a Graduation Cap, Books and Certificate. (Design Element and Symbol for School of Education).
 2. A Microscope, which is the Design Element and Symbol for School of Secondary Education (Science).
 3. A Composition of a Hand Holding a Spanner. Design Element and Symbol for School of Secondary Education (Technical)
 4. A Composition of a Paint Pallet, a Brush and a Pencil as was as a sewing machining Design Element and Symbol for School of Secondary Education (Vocational).
- Findings also revealed that the developed preliminary sketches and the working drawing reflected the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various departments of the college.
- Findings equally revealed that the selected design elements and symbols, which reflected the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various departments of the college was able to be utilized to produce a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate.

Discussion

This sculptural work is a collaborative study and an expression of visual narrative in three dimensional (3-d) art forms executed with a view to tackling the challenges of poor enrolment into the college. The art work was mounted at the main gate of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba.

The purpose of this study was to collaborate with sampled Schools and Departments in the College, to conduct a visual study that resulted in the production of a three dimensional (3-D) art form that was erected in front of the main gate of the college, with a view to tackling challenges of inadequate information about the college programmes through the use of public art. To this end, the study sought to determine from the inputs of sampled schools and departments, the design elements and symbols, that best portrayed the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the sampled Departments in the selected schools in the College, develop preliminary sketches, working drawings using inputs from sampled schools and departments, about the design elements and symbols, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the departments of the selected schools in the College, and then utilize the selected design elements and symbols, from sampled schools and departments, to produce a three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate.

The theme centers on a concept that was used to portray “*The programmes Mounted at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba*” theme was developed to depict the vision and mission of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba, and visualize a concept that carefully considers the programme of the college, and represented by the following sampled schools: School of Education, School of Secondary Education (Sciences), School of Secondary Education (Technical) and School of Secondary Education (Vocational).

The sculptural work is a three point two meters (3.2m) high edifice, mounted on two meters (2 meter) high pedestal. Cement was used as the medium of expression and direct modeling technique, was employed to achieve the objective of study.

Moreover the sculptural work was pertinated in black and gold to present a wrought-finish appearance.

The visual study utilized selected design elements and symbols, from sampled schools and departments, to produce three dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-rounds. One of the sampled schools was the School of Education which is viewed as the mother of all the schools in the college as it is a teacher educational institution, charged with the role of training vocational and technical teachers. To this end, a composition a graduation cap, a set of books and a certificate, the design element and symbol that was used to represent the school.

This design element was also used to reflect the overall goal of the programme mounted in the College and used to portray the production of graduates who possess the National Certificate in Education (NCE).

The second school sampled for the study, was the School of Secondary Education (Science). However Biology Department was sampled for the study. The design element and symbol that was used to represent the Department and the School was the microscope. The microscope is used to critically to analyze the activities of living things in their environment.

The third school sampled for the study, was the School of Secondary Education (Technical) and the Automobile Department was selected for the study. The design element and symbol adopted to represent the School was a composition of a hand holding a spanner. The spanner is one of the tools used by the Automobile Department as well as most departments in the school.

The fourth School sampled and selected for the study, was the School of Secondary Education (Vocational), in which the Department of Fine and Applied Arts Education was selected for the study. The two areas of the department were considered. To this end the following design elements and symbols adopted and used to represent the Department and the School. The first was the composition of a paint pallet, a brush and a pencil, which was used to portray Fine Arts unit of the Department. However, a sewing machining was also used to represent the Applied Art unit of the Department. Suffice to say that these items are also use in the Home Economics Department in the school.

The last design element and symbol adopted and used for the sculptural production was the College Logo. The College Logo is a composition of a hammer, a book, a type writer and a curb of maize. These items were used to represent three departments in these schools vis-à-vis Hammer (Technical) Maze (Agriculture) and the type writer (Business), as well as the book representing Education. Obviously, the College Logo seems to have been designed to capture the early programmes of the college.

Conclusion

The study would be developed from design elements and symbols, that best portrays the philosophy and objectives of the programmes mounted, in the various departments in the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba. The design elements and symbols are developed from inputs from various Departments, in the College. Preliminary sketches, working drawings and a Marquette (model) using the inputs from stakeholders, will be utilized. Moreover the study would utilize the art-based action research methodology to obtain information from various Departments that would result in the executing the final art work; a dimensional (3-D) sculpture-on-the-round in the front of the College main gate which is expected be informative enough to help improve the students' enrollment into the college.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby made:

- The artistic creativity of both staff and students of the Fine and Applied Arts Department, from the School of Vocational Education should deployed to produce a two dimensional (2-d) mural or mosaic art work on the fence of the Federal College of Education (Technical) Asaba towards further improving students enrolment into the college.
- More collaborative study should utilize the artistic creativity of both staff and students of the Fine and Applied Arts Department, from the School of Vocational Education together with the technical know-how of the staff and students of the School of Technical Education in the production of such outdoor sculptural work.
- More Tetfund research grants should be made available to sponsor similar researches in the feature, toward more action researches that is geared towards that development of the college.
- An assessment to ascertain the extent to which the project was able to achieve its objective should be conducted.

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